

8T – The Growth and Decay of Curvature Spikes

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July 14, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying (3,1) Lorentz manifold which experience arbitrary amount of curvature vanishing into matter, alongside the primordial coupling constants series, describing bosonic fields, analysis of two distinct kinds of curvature spikes will be presented. Curvature spikes with short lifetime decaying into matter in threefold combinations of two distinct elements, and stable curvature spikes associated with prime numbers with long lifetime. Those two spikes are predicted to grow over time on the matrix tensor as it expands given by the main equation.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Fermions are described by the arbitrary variation term on the main equation (1.3). By discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.31), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements that differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

In the context of curvature spikes, it is possible to construct the following for fermions. Curvature is not allowed and when it appears in a random unpredictable way, it vanishes immediately. Their lifetime is aspiring zero, and we can associate them to the fact that the universe is a part of a universe packet, causing each matric tensor to be flat. In the 8T, we used the Dirac delta to describe the process of arbitrary curvature vanishing into matter by equations (1.32) and (1.33):

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t) \quad (1.32)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.33)$$

Bosons are mentioned in the first paragraph are described as net curvature, given by the term (1.4):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.4)$$

Now, we since they are associated with prime numbers given by the primorial coupling series – (1.5) to (1.53) that cannot vanish into matter, their lifetime is stable and in fact infinite. They propagate all across the matric tensor, causing fermions to cluster. Overtime, more and more ripples across the matric tensor should appear, they should be weaker in the elements in the beginning of the series. The bosonic spikes are described by the equations (1.41) to (1.42).

$$\delta g = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.41)$$

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad \text{at} \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t + \Delta t) \quad (1.42)$$

$$\Delta t \rightarrow 0$$

$$\delta g = N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

The spikes are as you probability know by now are prime numbers, each prime is a discrete amount of net curvature, given by the primorial, equations (1.5) to (1.54).

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.5)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.51)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.52)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.53)$$

And in spin representation coming to an agreement with Planck constant and Stern and Einstein Discovery of 1913, that $a = 1/2$. Fermions can only emit and absorb quantities located on the prime critical line in the 8T framework as presented in equation (1.54) for the third coupling term.

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.54)$$

The first main point of this short essay is that according to the 8T, there are two main kinds of curvature spikes, the stable ones, associated with long lifetime and independence over the metric tensor. These are Bosons, which are infinite in kind proved by the primorial. The second are the exact opposite, the spikes vanish immediately and have short lifetime. These are curvature spikes unstable, associated with fermions. Another interesting question is whether the total amount of spikes both stable and unstable grow overtime. Regarding the second kind, the Bosonic spikes, it should grow overtime as the primorial is related to the arrow of time. that does not mean that the manifold gets more curved but rather more flat, given by ratio of net to total, aspiring zero. The same assumption could be made regarding unstable curvature spikes or fermions. There should be matter creation at all stages of development of the metric tensor. The term in equation (1.3) is not limited to a certain era of time. that is similar to operators of creation and destruction in QFT but much simpler as it only contains one term. Overall, this paper objective was to describe the features of each curvature spikes in terms of their stability and longevity. Three main ideas were presented

- (1) Stable curvature spikes with long lifetime are bosonic fields – independent on the metric tensor.
- (2) Vanishing curvature spikes of short life time – fermions. Two distinct elements, threefold combinations.
- (3) The metric tensor should experience curvature spikes of both kind with each stage of development. If the metric tensor increase in size, so does the amount of the spikes.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)